

CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR 6G

D1.5 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (V2)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The document addresses aspects pertaining to the Data Management Plan. CONFIDENTIAL 6G defined the data management process to be followed throughout the project at M6 (June 2022). This was done in the scope of D1.3 Data Management Plan. This document is meant to provide an update on the Data Management Plan. An overview of the work performed during the year since the first specification of the DMP (June 2023-June 2024), is provided. No data has been collected or processed and no human participants have been involved and therefore, the Consortium partners have not identified any new ethics issues that need to be addressed. Any possible impact on the data management plan and the associated processes recognized in the future, based on in-project discussions by the Consortium partners, will be used to re-adjust the project Data Management plan. Effort was made, to the extent possible, to revise this version of the document and include more specific information on types of data that will used, collected or generated, the data sources, where the data will be stored, etc. While the testing of the solutions developed in the project will be done in realistic use cases, testing will be performed only through emulated scenarios, strictly with the participation of partners involved in the project.